

Role of Emotional Intelligence on Employee Productivity with Mediating Effect of Workplace Stress in Public Sectors

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Abstract:

The core objective of this paper is to evaluate the role of emotional intelligence on employee productivity and the mediating role of workplace stress. If employees are conscious of their emotional state and sentiments and they are capable of identifying, understanding, and managing them according to the nature of workplace requirements they can perform more effectively and efficiently and it will enhance the productivity of the employees as well. Public sector employees can understand and appreciate the emotions of their colleagues. People having high emotional intelligence have a high level of productivity as compare to those having a low level of emotional intelligence. Good relationships among the employees and top management aid in enhancing employee productivity. For this study 300, public sector employees were selected and regression analysis was used for analyzing the results. From this study, it has been concluded that workplace stress as a mediator does not show any direct impact on employee productivity while employee intelligence and employee productivity have a strong and direct relationship. The public as well as private organizations, academic institutes will be able to recognize the extent of emotional intelligence in workers and how to amend the workplace environment to increase the awareness and level of emotional intelligence among employees to improve employee productivity. **Keywords:** Emotional intelligence, workplace stress, employee productivity.

1. Introduction:

Emotional intelligence comprises of ability that differentiates and generalizes emotions between you and others. (Goleman, 1998). Employees working in an organization show different negative and positive behaviors based on their emotional perception of behaviors and attitudes of others towards them (Dirican, 2019). The behaviors of other employees and managers strongly impact the behaviors of an individual as his emotional intelligence is exerting an influential force on his specific behaviors. But usually, it has been seen that emotional intelligence has been working constructively in shaping human behaviors (Oliver, 2019; Sendaro, 2019; Khosravi 2020). In an organizational scenario, the point of attention for an employee's emotional intelligence lies in the differences that how emotional intelligence is adopted by a human while he adopts the organizational environment.

On the other side, characteristic of emotional intelligence involves the skill of emotional intelligence as symptoms of self-efficacy in a person as the most common framework that incorporates skills of emotional intelligence. (Petrides, 2000). The productivity of employees increases as emotional intelligence increases. Self-efficacy in the performance of an employee is considered to be an influenced factor based on the strong emotional intelligence of the particular employee (Sendaro, 2019). Emotional intelligence creates a strong positive influential role in the evolution of employees believe in his professional ability to work in a competitive environment and deal with workplace stress much of the job needs the skills to manage the feelings (Thi, 2002; Rathi, 2009). However, many challenges are being confronted by workers in the public sectors of Pakistan.

Workplace stress is a significant aspect of employee productivity. If the stress increases on an employee he/she may lose their capabilities of being productive in their work (Gates, 2011). Well, stress can also be a source of motivation for some employees as it helps to shape their skills of uniqueness, creativity, and productivity due to which the problem of employee boredom also disappears (Bickford, 2005). Emotional intelligence helps to deal with workplace stress. This paper fills the gap that how EI plays a significant role in employee productivity.

The relationship between emotional intelligence is not only related to perceptive intelligence, success, or skill. But it is a sum of whole skills of life that we have acknowledged to be capable of managing ourselves. People with high emotional intelligence are capable to cope up with the environmental circumstances and workplace stress. (Ciarrochi 2006).

The main purpose of this paper is to examine the employees who very intelligent emotionally and tend to achieve the best outcomes from their job, particularly trending situations that aid in understanding how to manage emotions. Emotional intelligence influence the work in the condition of workplace stress for the organizational development to examine the potential significance particularly advanced skills of management help via literature to recognize.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Emotional Intelligence

The concept of emotional intelligence reformed the philosophy of administration science across culture and industry after its emergence although this concept appeared very late in administration science. IQ and EI are perceived and argued to be different from each other rather than being opposite to each other. According to researches, individuals must possess a combination of both IQ and EI for their success in any fields of life. Individuals who have more IQ ad compared to EI are perceived to be less successful in their fields of life. Concept of emotional intelligence was introduced by Salovey and Mayer (1990). Individuals having less mature knowledge of emotional intelligence as compared to IQ will be less progressive in their no matter what the field they have selected for their future. It shows that knowledge of emotional intelligence is critical for the success of business individuals.

Emotional intelligence is a well-known point for the present administration and hierarchical conduct scientists by giving extreme headings to administer individuals in workplace excellently. Execution can be amplified (Goleman, 1998) and passionate abilities can be increased in the job capacity of individuals with the help of emotional intelligence as both of them are major substantial issues for administration. Results of work are also influenced by eager knowledge (for example Wong and Law, 2002; Goleman et al., 2002). Book of Daniel Goldman gave fame to the concept of passionate intelligence but many scientists had their role and participation in the hypothesis and research. Four branch model of passionate insight was specified by John John Mayer, Peter Salovey, and David Caruso. Mayer and Salovey (1997). The first branch is the overseeing feelings to accomplish explicit objectives. The second branch is getting feelings, passionate language, and the signs passed on through feelings. The third branch is utilizing feelings to encourage thinking and the last one is seeing feelings precisely in oneself as well as other people.

Emotional intelligence administrators are self-roused and stimulated as well as make others around submitted and persuaded towards function also.

2.2. Workplace stress:

It is an intricate psychological component, the idea of which can be understood by first comprehending its parent concept called stress. The feeling of stress is described as the alteration in a person's physical or psychological state in response to challenging or threatening stressors or circumstances (Krantz et al., 1985; Zimbardo et al., 2003). There are situations when we have to face demanding situations that need a great deal of physical and psychological exertion. In addition, workplace stress may also become overwhelming for a person leading to serious emotional suffering and physical infirmity. Essentially, stress has been classified into two categories;

1. Eustress
2. Distress.

Eustress is also considered positive stress. The word 'Eu' came from the Greek word meaning 'good' (Seyle, 1980). As stress is naturally a response, the stressor related to it is cognitively considered to be constructive or complex.

On the other hand, distress is the stress response to the stressors considered negative. As with most people, stress is thought to be the time when they are either afflicted with unpleasant situations that imposes pressure on them and affects their performance, when an untoward incident occurs or when they have to deal with day-to-day stressors that cause general frustration.

Lazarus and Folkman described the stress, the properties of the stressors, and the physiological, psychological, and cultural characteristics of a person (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). The Response of an individual on the cognitive, sensational, physiological, and behavioral level is influenced by the association between individual stressors with the resources and stress characteristics. When an individual is unable to adapt and adjust to the stressors, it results in long-lasting psychological, emotional, and physical complications some of which can be dangerous (Zimbardo et al., 2003). According to Lazarus (2000), stress is the result of a situation that needs behavior adaptation. This means that the physiological response to any change; whether good or bad, positive or negative, is the same. The perception and feeling of stress use the energy and defensive resources of the body with time as the stress duration prolongs. This results in the utilization and depletion of these resources. As described by Lazarus (2000), the categories of stress include acute stress, chronic stress as well as episodic stress.

Each stress level is connected to its psychological and emotional stress. Acute stress takes place when challenges, pressures, and prospects are imposed on a person and these challenges are beyond their adaptive threshold. These challenges appear as impractical and unworkable work demands and unanticipated meetings which lead to endeavors for work completion and further circumstances which may be the source of frustration but are short-lived in general.

There are the following symptoms of Acute Stress:

- Frustration,
- Hostility and
- Increased anxiety

The physical symptoms of acute stress are temporary high blood pressure, increased heart rate, fatigue, lightheadedness, and headache, and back pain, pain in the jaw, confusion, and inability to focus. The symptoms of acute stress have an obvious offset and onset (Zimbardo et al., 2003). Episodic stress is inclusive of the conditions of acute stress; though, the stress occurs with the higher frequency and consistency in several incidents. The individual who undergoes episodic stress will show signs of lack of tolerance, violence, eagerness, and a feeling of urgency.

In contrast, stress is not bad all the time. Sometimes stress can also facilitate you to remain alert, energized, and facilitates you to fulfill challenges at the office. Stress is what makes you brisk and careful if you have a presentation or keeps you alert in order to prevent misfortune or mistakes. However, in our fast-paced planet, the stress at work time and again shakes emotionally as well as physically. Extended time at the workplace, short deadlines, as well as increasingly demanding work needs tend to drain you, anxious and burdened. It is when stress surpassed your capability to adapt and manage things that stop being supportive and cause harm to your body along with mind and undermines your job fulfillment. Workplace stress is the result of a mismatch between the demands of the role of your potential aptitude and resources as well as the available support.

Even though you cannot get control of everything at the workplace in the midst of a challenging situation, that really doesn't mean you have no power. However, make sure that if the workplace stress is what's interfering with your performance, personal life, or health, you should take action. There is a lot that can be done to

decrease the amount of your stress and recover your feeling of being in control at work, regardless of what your field is, what your aspirations are or how much demanding your job is.

Stress-related to work is the response of an individual when the work demands are laid down, when the pressures unmatched to one's knowledge are anticipated and when unmanageable challenges are presented. Although stress can occur in a variety of work circumstances, it worsens when the employees think that they have a low level of support from the management, supervisors, and colleagues as well as with a sense of having less power on the procedures.

On the contrary, commonly there lies uncertainty between challenges, difficulty, and stress and at times this is used as a justification for poor organizational practices. It is inevitable to avoid workplace pressure because of the contemporary needs of the present-day work setting. Based on the available assets and individual character, the strain can be considered as acceptable by a person and may even facilitate employees to stay alert, motivated, and keen to learn. Nevertheless, when that pressure or strain turns out to be exceedingly disproportionate and undoable, it converts into stress. Stress then can spoil workers' performance as well as health.

Workplace stress can be brought about by inadequate organization at work; the manner in which jobs and systems are configured and the approach with which they are managed. This also occurs due to poor work design, less control over work procedures, as an example, unsatisfactory working environment poor management, and inadequate support from supervisors and colleagues.

Research shows that the most stressful working environment is the one in which excessive work demands are valued, unmatched pressures are imposed on workers, there is a lack of prospect exercise any control in where there is a low level of support.

There is a less likelihood of employees to be stressed out in demanding situations at their job when the tasks match their capabilities in addition to knowledge some level of control can be exercised and how they do their work when the supervisors in please provide support to them and when the employees have a role in decision making concerning their designated work.

Productivity is the measure of performance of both proficiency and viability. Workers are keen to be involved in decision-making, critical thinking activities, and the setting of goals. It has been found that better performance is prompted by the active participation of workers (Hellriegel, Slocum, and Woodman, 1998). As of today, management that promotes participation increases employee productivity and fulfillment (Madison, Wisconsin, 2000). Employee contribution is highly affected by job satisfaction as well as efficiency. However, satisfaction is highly affected by this as paralleled to productivity (Miller and Monge, 1986).

2.3. Emotional intelligence and employee productivity:

In multiple studies, it has been concluded from the previous times like (Bar-On, 1997b, 2004, 2006a, 2006b; Bar-On, Handley & Fund, 2006; Handley, 1997; Ruderman & Bar-On, 2003), positive relationship between employee's productivity and emotional intelligence has been presented. From these studies 55% of average validity is predicted, it means that almost thirty percent of employee productivity depends on emotional intelligence.

In organizational conditions, there are various components and factors that impact employee efficiency, participation, turnover, motivation at work, and significantly the culture of the organization. One of the factors that are been the focus is stress among employees in the organizational setting. It has been proven by the research that pressure and stress at the workplace are contrarily identified with satisfaction with the job, commitment with organization, profitability, and motivation. Further studies have correspondingly uncovered that stress is decidedly identified with a dysfunctional working environment and turnover in the environment of an organization (Pipe, et al., 2009).

2.4. Emotional Intelligence & workplace Stress

EI might be considered as the main differentiator with regards to overseeing worry in the working environment. Genuinely canny workforces have inclinations to see and decipher an undermining situation diversely and furthermore to discover successful answers for it.

Ogniska-Bulik (2005) reports that the ability to viably manage feelings and emotional data in the work environment helps representatives in adapting to work-related stress and pressure; in this manner, it ought to be created in trainings of stress management. In this way, the implications of these discoveries are to assist workers to build up their degree of EI and become compelling at their job place. Emotionally intelligent people can keep up constructive mental states because of their capacity to adequately and profitably deal with their feelings. Training for EI might be helpful in decreasing pressure and improving wellbeing, prosperity, and executions at the job place.

The procedure and results of EI advancement contain numerous components known to lessen stress, for both people and organizations, by minimizing clash; helping to comprehend and connecting people in relations; and cultivating strength, congruity, and agreement. Five areas of EI cover personal and social competence that is mindfulness, self-guiding, self-inspiration, social mindfulness, and social aptitudes skills. To sum things up, these aspects identify with knowing emotions and feelings of self; dealing with those feelings; persuading self; perceiving and understanding others' feelings; and management of relations, i.e., dealing with the feelings and emotions of others.

Emotional intelligence was intended to particularly assess by using self-report the seven components of a person's emotional intelligence (1) mindfulness/self-awareness, monitoring one's sentiments and handling them (2) emotional versatility or resilience, having the option to keep up with one's performance under any kind of pressure (3) individual motivation having the determination and vitality to accomplish aspiring objectives or aims (4) personal sensitivity, which demonstrates compassion and sympathy towards others (5) influence or impact which impacting and convincing others to acknowledge one's perspectives or offers (6) intuitiveness or perception, making reasonable decisions and instinct when suitable and (7) conscientiousness or diligence that is being steady in one's life and activities, and carrying on as indicated by winning moral and values.

Emotional intelligence is categorized into four varied characteristics on the base of Mayer & Salovey (1997) and Salovey & Mayer (1990), Wong and Law (2002). These are categorized as (i) Self-emotional appraisal and evaluation: This characteristic is identified as appraisal and expression of one's own sentiments and feelings. (ii) Others' emotional appraisal and identification: This aspect is defined as the comprehension and understanding of the feelings of individuals surrounding that person. (iii). Regulation of self-emotion: This dimension is recognized as the capacity of individuals to regulate and control their sentiments. (iv). Utilization of emotions to facilitate performance: This aspect is associated with the ability people to use their emotions so as to enhance their own performance as well as employees' productivity.

The model proposed by (Salovey and Mayer, 1990) distinguishes four unique factors of Emotional Intelligence: The ability to identify emotions, the capability of reasoning the sentiments, understanding emotions, and being able to regulate feelings. As described by Salovey and Mayer, the four dimensions of their model are, "categorized from fundamental psychological procedures to more complex, highly coordinated procedures.

For example, the first level dimension is concerned with the simple ability of man to perceive and express emotions. Comparatively, the highest level is related to the higher cognitive, regulation of emotions. The details of these elements are as follows (Salovey and Mayer, 2000) (Caruso, 2006): 1). Emotions understanding: The initial stage in the acknowledgment of emotions is their comprehension appropriately. By and large, it may include appreciating non-verbal signs like facial expressions and body language. 2). Rationality in emotions: The following level deals with utilizing sentiments to enhance reasoning and reasoning behavior. It is the emotions that direct our priorities and actions; our reactions are based on feelings for the things that earn our attention. 3). Understand emotions: The feelings that we have to hold a wide host of connotations. If an

individual is showing anger the observer must infer the reason behind that anger and what it may actually mean. For example, if your boss gets angry at you, it may be the expression of visitor dissatisfaction with your work or it could be because of a bad start of the day like, a speeding ticket on his way to the office or a fight with his wife. 4). Managing emotions: the ability to manage and regulate emotions efficiently is the primary component of emotional intelligence. Regulation of emotions, reacting appropriately, and responding to the feelings of other individuals are all essential parts of emotional management.

2.5.Theoretical framework

2.5.1. Socio technical System Theory

This theory suggests that people in an organization work in a multi-social environment; where people of different capabilities, skills, ideologies, and knowledge work together to fulfill the motives of the organization (Smith, 2010). In such an environment where different minds are working together there is high competition for being more productive for the organization and being more successful which created an environment of pressure on employees mind and working abilities; in such a situation if he/she is emotionally stable to handle the work pressure and be productive in his job only then his survival is possible (Bently, 2016).

Form a study conducted by Smith (2010), it was seen that the socio-technical system has helped the organizations to develop a system where employees working in chains of the network; work in collaboration, cooperation, and tolerance towards each other. Such a system provides a chance for the employees to work competitively and learn the skills of being more productive while being calmer and relax at a job (Dow, 2017). About an employee's productivity it can be stated that as long as he can control pressures on his mind and be able to devise solutions to coming issues constructively he can resultantly be more productive at his job.

When employees feel more overloaded with work pressure the socio community of workers surrounding him becomes a learning source for him for managing a bundle of tasks and being more efficient while delivering services to the organization. Socio-technical system theory implies a concept in organizations that whenever employees work in collaboration with other highly competitive employees there mental capacity of being mature, more balanced and creative at work are created which helps them to improve their intellectual and intelligence at work (Guerre, 2008); and this mental fitness of an employee is necessary for attaining an effective performance of an employee. Such type of system does not reduce the level of stress of an employee the implication of this theory into a working environment helps to manage the workplace stress more constructively (Carayon, 2006).

This theory in an organization helps to improve the employee's mental health by exerting a sense of self-efficacy that helps an employee to improve his intelligence while being effectively productive for his organization by stabilizing the level of work pressure constructively.

This theory in an organization creates a system in which when an employee works in a chain of a networked system where all the employees are working in collaboration with other highly competitive, skilled, and knowledge-seeking employees and brings improvement to his skills. Working in such a highly competitive and intellectual environment helps to integrate into an employee self-intelligence of being equal competitive of others, handling the stress of work and competition which ultimately improves an employee performing ability.

2.5.1. Theoretical Framework

2.6. Hypothesis Development

H1: Emotional Intelligence has a direct impact on Employee Productivity

As long as emotional intelligence is greater in any employee his motivation to perform his job as well as his ability to be useful and productive at his job increases (Dirican, 2019). It is also a determinant of the level of performance exerted by an employee on his job; with high emotional intelligence the employee would have high emotional stability and due to his emotional stability he is capable of handling pressure works and hurdles in all kind of organizational processes (Khosravi, 2020). While an employee is working in a competitive environment it is very necessary for them to be productive and for being productive the mental stability is an essential element which can be achieved through his strong emotional intelligence as stated by Oliver (2019), further he has elaborated that emotional intelligence for an employee is important as it creates an environment of flexibility, acceptance towards each action and thus it becomes a success factor for the employees.

H2: Emotional Intelligence has a strong effect on the mediating effect of workplace stress on employee productivity

When an employees' productive ability starts weakening in his organizational performance he may feel stressed out because at this his abilities, skills and knowledge is not working in accordance with the demand of the organization and at this time his motivation level returns with is strong emotional intelligence that lower the emotional instability in workplace, converts the workplace stress in a constructive manner and helps the employee to put back his productivity in his work (Ismail, 2009). Bad performance of an employee or competitive environment in an organization weakens down the employee performance in an organization and this instability of performance can be reduced through different pieces of training on emotional intelligence where workplace stress is used to increase the motivation level of employee to perform more actively, effectively and efficiently (Slaski, et. al. 2003).

H3: EI has a strong impact on Workplace Stress

Workplace stress can impact the daily work life of an employee by affecting his emotional balance and creating pressure on his abilities and skills which can be found to be reduced through the emotional stability of an employee during his work. It has been stated by Ashkanasy, et, al. (2003), that to reduce the workplace stress the training of emotional intelligence helps the employees to put the right step and make the right decision in

pressure situations. A study conducted by I. Nikolau and I. Tsaosis, (2002) has stated that there is an inverse relationship between emotional intelligence and workplace stress; with the increase of emotional intelligence, there is a decrease in workplace stress.

H4: workplace stress impact on employee productivity

As long as employees are given training on stress management and their capabilities of stress handling are strong their productivity in a competitive environment will be up to mark (Gates, et.al. 2011). Workplace stress is a constructive mechanism that helps the employees to be more skilled in pressure handlings as well as being more quick and active in their performances (Kompier, et.al.2012). Organizational work stress has helped the employees to be more attentive to their work, more active in their doings, and more productive in their performances (Sorana, 2014).

3. Methodology

The methodology for research is the comprehensive description of the phases and the adoptions at every level leading to the research (Sanders, D. E. 2009). The approach for research in this paper is structured and organized according to Saunders' research layers.

3.1. Research Technique

Exploratory research technique is applied to this study as the objective of this study is to test a theory with the help of other variables. Survey questionnaires are used to gather and analyze data in exploratory research.

3.2. Research Approach

One research approach is selected in this phase. Inductive approach and deductive approach are the two available options and types of the research approach. The deductive approach will be used in this study because it is a quantitative study. Whenever data is gathered from questionnaires surveys that are established on the base comprehensive accepted theory, the deductive approach is used.

3.3 Research Strategy

A causal or explanatory research strategy is utilized in this study. When research is based on an academic theory that is universal and acknowledged by everyone, then a causal research strategy is used. Questionnaire surveys are used to further investigate the theory with the help of some variables.

3.5 Time Horizons

Types of research are used as a basis for selecting the time horizons. Longitudinal and Cross-sectional are varieties of research horizons. A single meeting is conducted to approach the respondents in quantitative analysis. So, a meeting will be conducted in this study to approach the respondents because the cross-sectional time horizon is selected in this study.

3.6 Research Method

The facts and figures gathered after analyzing the provided size of the sample will be measured to analyze the data gathered in this study because it is a quantitative study.

3.7 Population

The employees of the public sector of Pakistan are considered as the target population for this study. These public sector employees were those employees who were serving in big cities of Pakistan: Karachi, Lahore, Islamabad, and Multan. These cities were selected as the employees working in these cities have more workload on them; they have to deal with a wide population matter residing in these cities.

3.8 Sample Size

350 questionnaires were distributed among the employees of public sector out of which 300 are received back. Response rate was 85%.

3.9 Sampling Design Strategy

Probability and non-probability are two types of sampling strategies. The sampling strategy is selected for the purpose of choosing the size of the sample. The strategy selected and used in this study is the probability sampling strategy. The random sampling strategy was chosen from the two available types of probability sampling strategy. Every individual has an equal chance of getting participation in a research study in a random sampling technique.

3.10 Measures:

Scales used in this paper have been ascertained valid and reliable in the previous researches are chosen for all three variables presented in this paper.

Emotional intelligence was measured by utilizing a 5-point scale constitute of thirty-three items Solvey & Mayer (1990) Emotional intelligence scale ranging from 1=strongly Disagree – 5=Strongly agree.

To examine the mediating role of workplace stress a 5 point WSS (The workplace stress scale) is developed by The Marlin Company, North Haven, Connecticut, and The American Institute of Stress, Yonkers, New York. Ranging from 1=Neverly, 2=rarely, 3=Sometimes, 4=Often, 5=Very often. Only 8 questions were related to the current research.

To examine the outcomes of **employee productivity**, a 5 point gossip scale constitute of 3 items options ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree. The results of this study are analyzed with the help of the SPSS software 26 version. The reliability of the collected data will be checked with the help of the initial Cronbach alpha. The hypothesis will be tested by using the Correlation and Regression Analysis.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 Reliability:

The reliability of responses collected is measured to analyze the dependability in answers given by the respondents. To measure the reliability of the responses, the value of Cronbach alpha is calculated. The value of Cronbach alpha obtained is 0.679 which means that data is reliable.

4.1 table of Reliability Statistics

Cronbach alpha	No. of items
.679	44

4.2 Exploratory Factor Analysis

Structures designed of the factor for the relevant measured variables are identified with the help of exploratory factor analysis. Results are collected after measuring the correlations of the variables. Constructs are formed on the basis of these results. The relationship between the factor items of variables and constructs is developed with the help of EFA. The table is utilized for this matrix of correlation. Covariance described by the variables is shown by the values gathered from the correlation matrix.

4.2.1. Correlation Matrix

4.2.1. Correlation Matrix

Measures	1	2	3
1. P	1		
2. EI	.609**	1	
3. WS	.541**	.110*	1

In this table value of Pearson correlation (r) shows the relationship of variables with each other. The values should remain between -1 and +1. From the table above the value obtained for correlation are significant as they lie between -1 and $+1$.

4.2.2 KMO and Bartlett test:

The sampling adequacy of all the variables comprised is tested by conducting the KMO test in the data analysis. Its values are ranged from 0 to 1. The adequate values of KMO are above 0.6 to 0.7.

4.2.2. KMO Test

KMO nad Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin		.074
Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	12558.312
df		946
Sig		.000

4.2.3. Communalities

4.2.3. Table of communality

This table shows the value of items of components of variables, which should be above 0.4. Any value below 0/4 shown in the table will be excluded from further analysis.

	Communalities	
	Initial	Extraction
E1	1.000	.590
E2	1.000	.618
E3	1.000	.568
E4	1.000	.735
E5	1.000	.646
E6	1.000	.798
E7	1.000	.661
E8	1.000	.571
E9	1.000	.812
E10	1.000	.584
E11	1.000	.682
E12	1.000	.695
E13	1.000	.714
E14	1.000	.751
E15	1.000	.717
E16	1.000	.656
E17	1.000	.649
E18	1.000	.673
E19	1.000	.566
E20	1.000	.643
E21	1.000	.708
E22	1.000	.568
E23	1.000	.561
E24	1.000	.639
E25	1.000	.679
E26	1.000	.599
E27	1.000	.568
E28	1.000	.616
E29	1.000	.619
E30	1.000	.627
E31	1.000	.696
E32	1.000	.673
E33	1.000	.669
W1	1.000	.595
W2	1.000	.639
W3	1.000	.635
W4	1.000	.671
W5	1.000	.755
W6	1.000	.599
W7	1.000	.659
W8	1.000	.538
P1	1.000	.681
P2	1.000	.742
P3	1.000	.602

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

In this table there is no such value of any component of any variable that lies below 0.4 so no values are exclude from further analysis.

4.2.4. Total Variance Explained

4.2.4. Table of total variance explained

This table shows all the values of variance shown by variables. The eigenvalues of factors above 1 are important to be studies in further analysis of the study which can be observed through sum of cumulative% obtained.

Component	Total Variance Explained					
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Total
1	7.319	16.635	16.635	7.319	16.635	16.635
2	3.110	7.069	23.703	3.110	7.069	23.703
3	2.112	4.801	28.504	2.112	4.801	28.504
4	1.789	4.065	32.569	1.789	4.065	32.569
5	1.780	4.046	36.615	1.780	4.046	36.615
6	1.520	3.454	40.068	1.520	3.454	40.068
7	1.400	3.181	43.250	1.400	3.181	43.250
8	1.348	3.064	46.313	1.348	3.064	46.313
9	1.289	2.931	49.244	1.289	2.931	49.244
10	1.180	2.682	51.926	1.180	2.682	51.926
11	1.146	2.605	54.531	1.146	2.605	54.531
12	1.098	2.496	57.027	1.098	2.496	57.027
13	1.058	2.405	59.432	1.058	2.405	59.432
14	1.051	2.390	61.821	1.051	2.390	61.821
15	1.002	2.277	64.098	1.002	2.277	64.098
16	.978	2.222	66.320			
17	.969	2.203	68.523			
18	.917	2.083	70.606			
19	.879	1.997	72.603			
20	.804	1.827	74.430			
21	.771	1.752	76.182			
22	.747	1.697	77.879			
23	.706	1.604	79.482			
24	.694	1.577	81.060			
25	.676	1.536	82.595			
26	.651	1.479	84.074			
27	.608	1.382	85.456			
28	.569	1.293	86.749			
29	.546	1.242	87.991			
30	.533	1.211	89.202			
31	.531	1.206	90.408			
32	.467	1.061	91.469			
33	.443	1.007	92.476			
34	.428	.973	93.449			
35	.386	.877	94.326			
36	.372	.845	95.171			
37	.330	.749	95.921			
38	.322	.731	96.652			
39	.310	.705	97.357			
40	.286	.649	98.006			
41	.246	.559	98.566			
42	.229	.520	99.086			
43	.213	.484	99.569			
44	.190	.431	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

4.3.5. Rotated Component Matrix

This table shows us the values of factor loadings of items of variables. If the items are loaded on their own variables then their values are accepted but if the values of loadings are shown on other variables then they are excluded.

Rotated Component Matrix

	Emotional Intelligence	Workplace Stress	Employee Productivity
E1	.756		
E2	.658		
E3	.754		
E4	.748		
E5	.643		
E6	.678		
E7	.834		
E8	.632		
E9	.684		
E10	.685		
E11	.824		
E12	.818		
E13	.712		
E14	.765		
E15	.841		
E16	.775		
E17	.657		
E18	.724		
E19	.671		
E20	.817		
E21	.842		
E22	.690		
E23	.712		
E24	.752		
E25	.847		

E26	.729	
E27	.706	
E28	.621	
E29	.815	
E30	.608	
E31	.749	
E32	.694	
E33	.821	
W1	.628	
W2	.700	
W3	.634	
W4	.684	
W5	.643	
W6	.825	
W7	.724	
W8	.662	
P1		.601
P2		.720
P3		.854

From the above table of rotated component matrix, the values of loadings are acceptable as no factor has shown loadings on other variables.

4.3 Regression Analysis

Regression Analysis is executed for analyzing this study. The relationship and effects that exist between the variables are assessed with regression analysis. The relationship between variables is known after analyzing the model summary of the values of R, R^2 , and adjusted R^2 . The extent to which an independent variable can be foreseen through a dependent variable is indicated by the value of R. The value of R^2 , which is the coefficient of determination, is estimated. The level of variance of a dependent variable which can be determined through the value of an independent variable is specified by the coefficient of determination. The improvement of the relationship established is viewed and analyzed with the help of the adjusted value of R^2 . The value of an independent variable is used to estimate the measure of a dependent variable thorough assessment of the value of the level of variance of an independent variable and dependent variable.

4.3.1. Multicollinearity

Liner accuracy of variables is tested with the help of the results of collinearity statistics in data analysis. The presence of multi-collinearity between the variables is tested by performing this test. Value of Variance Inflation Factor and Tolerance Factor is investigated in the value of this test. The accepted value to tolerance test is less than 0.10. The accepted value of the Variance Inflation Factor is more than 10. Multi-collinearity seems to be non- problematic if the value of tolerance is low and the value of VIF is high.

All the factors of variables are a part of this study. No item is eliminated from the analysis because all of them are having factor values above Multicollinearity:

4.3.1. Collinearity Statistics

Collinearity Statistics		
	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)		
Emotional Intelligence	.987	1.103

This table shows that there is no collinearity among the variables of this study.

4.3.2. Correlation

4.3.2. Table of correlation

It is an assumption of regression analysis which states that no variable should be correlated to each other. And for verifying this assumption the value of Durbin Watson is checked which should be between 0-4.

Variable	Durbin Watson Values
Employee Productivity	1.467
Emotional Intelligence	1.546
Workplace Stress	1.724

As the values of all the variables lie between 0-4 it means there is very less or no correlation among the selected variables.

4.3.4. ANOVA Test

4.3.4 Table of ANOVA Test

This table shows the level of significance of variables which should be at .000 proving that the values are 95% significant.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	86.948	5	17.390	184.509	.000b
	Residual	32.421	344	.094		
	Total	119.369	349			

The results of the anova test shows that significant value of test is .000 which shows that value of variables is 95% correct to be used for the further analysis.

4.3.5. Model Summary

4.3.5. Table of regression analysis

R	R ₂	adjusted R ₂
.733	.622	.808

It shows that the variance of independent variable employee productivity is 73% explained through the independent variable employee intelligence. So it means that the independent variable has a direct and noteworthy influence on the dependent variable.

4.3.6. Table of coefficients

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	sig.
	B	Std. Error	B		
(Constant)	.464	.083		3.450	.001
Emotional Stress	.396	.045	.542	4.152	.000

The values of coefficient shows that with 1 unit increase in the value independent variable there will be an increase in the value of dependent variable.

4.4 Mediation Analysis

To check the direct and indirect impact of variables, mediation analysis is performed through which the values of indirect and direct relationship obtained show how more or less strong relationships of variables exist.

For the mediation analysis Hayes model has been used in this study. According to Hayes's model, the direct relation between dependent and independent variables shows positive and direct relation with a value of .0576 it means that employee productivity has a direct and positive relationship with independent variable emotional intelligence. So we can say here, that with the increasing emotional intelligence in employees the employee productivity will also increase.

The indirect effect obtained through mediation analysis shows the value of -.0002 which means there is a weak relationship of mediating variable workplace stress with the independent and dependent variable. This result shows that variable emotional intelligence directly impacts employee productivity but the mediating variable workplace stress does not have any mediating effect on emotional intelligence and employee productivity.

4.4.1. Hayes Model of Mediation

5. Conclusion

From this study, it has been concluded that workplace stress as a mediator does not show any effect on employee productivity and it does not enhance the impact of emotional intelligence on the dependent variable employee productivity. So the hypothesis H2 has been rejected as the mediator does not show any direct and significant relationship with the independent and dependent variable.

In this study, the analysis has shown that employee productivity is directly affected by the independent variable emotional intelligence. So with the increasing emotional intelligence of an employee, his performance will be positively affected. So from this result, it is clear that H1 is approved.

From this study, it has been estimated that workplace stress as a mediating variable does not create any effect on employee productivity, and as a mediating variable it does not enhance the emotional intelligence of employees. But, workplace stress relationship with the variable employee productivity and emotional intelligence of employees. So in this study H2 is rejected while H3 and H4 are accepted.

Limitations

This study was based on public sector employees of Pakistan but as these variables are most important aspects of the organizational environment so further research on private-sector employees working in the educational sector, banking sector or IT departments can also be conducted and specific study in comparison of region to the region its impact can be explored. This study was a quantitative study so the next research can also be done through a qualitative technique to get a more detailed understanding of these variables. Another important point in this study is that mediation results are negative so further research can also be conducted by choosing another variable as mediator. All three variables have never seen before in such a relationship in past studies. In previous researches, emotional intelligence used as a mediator or moderator between job stress and employee performance but no work has been done on workplace stress yet where emotional intelligence is an independent variable directly affecting employee productivity.

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